

Studies on magnetic behavior of a sample obtained from polymeric precursor technique

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Abstract : It was possible to achieve yttrium barium copper oxide ($Y_1Ba_2Cu_4O_8$) by polymeric precursor technique using sodium polyacrylate. In this present investigation, material obtained by polymeric precursor technique, is washed with distilled water for several times and dried and magnetic measurements have been carried out. It has been found that ferromagnetic behavior is indicated at 77 K and XRD study indicates presence of $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$, barium oxide and sodium oxide in the mixture.

Keywords : Polymeric precursor, polyvalent metal ion, ferromagnetism, moment, X-ray diffraction study.

Introduction

Aqueous solution of guar gum-graft-acrylamide (G-g-Am) has been found to bind polyvalent metal ion at different pH range¹. COO^- groups are mainly responsible for binding polyvalent metal ion by G-g-Am²⁻⁴. So sodium polyacrylate may be the better choice. Sodium polyacrylate has been used to prepare yttrium barium copper oxide ($Y_1Ba_2Cu_4O_8$) by polymeric precursor technique⁵. Material obtained is washed with distilled water for several times and then dried and submitted for magnetic measurements and then for X-ray diffraction (XRD) study. Magnetic measurements show indication of ferromagnetic behavior at 77 K. Thus this material may be useful. XRD study indicates presence of $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ (superconducting material), barium oxide and sodium oxide in the mixture.

Materials and brief methods :

Yttrium barium copper oxide has been prepared by polymeric precursor

technique using aqueous solution of sodium polyacrylate, $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution, $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution and $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution and raising pH by NaOH solution to get precipitate. To remove polymeric part, material is heated to 1000 °C for 1 h. Technique has been reported already⁵. XRD study with the material obtained in this process indicated presence of $Y_1Ba_2Cu_4O_8$ with barium oxide⁵. In this present investigation materials is washed with distilled water for several times and when washing does not give heavy white precipitate by adding potassium pyroantimonate solution, it is dried and then submitted for magnetic measurements and then for XRD. MPMS SQUID VSM (Magnetic Property Measurement System using Superconducting Quantum Interference Device and Vibrating Sample Magnetometer) has been used to check magnetic properties. Approximately 2.7 mg sample is used for magnetic measurements. Sample is cooled in zero field from 300 K to 5 K. A field (200 oersted) is imposed to get curve for zero field cooling and curve for high field cooling.

In moment vs field case, set temperature was 77 K and following variations are considered.

0	—————→	3000 oersted
3000 oersted	—————→	50,000 oersted
50,000 oersted	—————→	3000 oersted
3000 oersted	—————→	-3000 oersted
-3000 oersted	—————→	-50,000 oersted
-50,000 oersted	—————→	-3000 oersted
-3000 oersted	—————→	3000 oersted
3000 oersted	—————→	50,000 oersted

XRD study has been carried out with powdered sample using the instrument X' Part PRO [Company → PANalytical (Holland)], target was copper and with low angle proportional detector.

Results and discussion

XRD :

XRD pattern of the sample is shown in Fig. 1. Many peaks match with yttrium barium copper oxide [chemical formula $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ (orthor-

hombic) superconducting material]. Some peaks match with barium oxide and some peaks match with sodium oxide. Positions of the peaks matching with $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ are shown in Fig. 2. Positions of the peaks matching with barium oxide are shown in Fig. 3. Positions of the peaks matching with sodium oxide are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of the material obtained after washing and drying.

Magnetic measurements :

Moment vs temperature plots are shown in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5 at near about 300 K, there is bifurcation of two curves. This is probably due to difference in alignments in two cases.

At set temperature 77 K, in moment vs field plot (Fig. 6) material is behaving as a ferromagnetic substance. 77 K is chosen because $Y_1Ba_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ shows superconductivity at 77 K.

Fig. 2. Positions of the peaks matching with Y₁Ba₂Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}.

Fig. 3. Positions of the peaks matching with barium oxide.

Fig. 4. Positions of the peaks matching with sodium oxide.

Fig. 5. Moment vs temperature plots.

Fig. 6. Moment vs field plot at set temperature 77 K.

Conclusion

Work on ceramic magnet is important in Materials Science. This work indicated material obtained by polymeric precursor technique as reported earlier⁵, on washing with distilled water and drying, helps to give a material with ferromagnetic nature at 77 K. So its crystal structure is important. Analysis on XRD indicates $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ is a superconducting material. So this work may open a new area in research.

References

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